

Curation and Analysis of 'XVIIIe siècle: Bibliographie'

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Introduction

Subject bibliographies support the creation of quantitative overviews (e.g. Luhmann and Burghardt, 2021) and qualitative surveys (e.g. Schöch et al., 2023) of a given field. In turn, bibliometrics, i.e. the statistical analysis of bibliographic datasets, provides insights into the history and characteristics of publication activities, but also into the methods and pitfalls of such analyses and the risks of relying on bibliometric indicators for performance assessment (e.g. van Raan, 2019). The value of open bibliographic data is also articulated clearly and programmatically (e.g. Peroni et al., 2015).

Motivated by this background, the present contribution describes one particular bibliography, the *XVIIIe siècle: Bibliographie*, its transformation into a structured dataset, and some results from an analysis of this dataset. The project website provides more information about the project and all resources mentioned below: <https://christofs.github.io/BIB18/>.

The poster aims to showcase the unique resource represented by the *XVIIIe siècle: Bibliographie*, to provide insight into strategies for the curation of bibliographic data (as well as some of the challenges involved in the process), and to highlight key findings about the publication habits of the research community whose work is documented by the bibliography.

The *XVIIIe siècle: Bibliographie*

The *XVIIIe siècle: Bibliographie* has been published, since 1992, and in over 550 instalments, by Canadian literary scholar Benoît Melançon. The bibliography is focused on scholarly publications about the Eighteenth century, both in French and in other languages. Members of the community can submit publications using an online form, making this a community-driven resource. This process, however, means there is no attempt at complete or systematic coverage and may also be a source of biases. In early 2023, Benoît Melançon published a complete set of all references for the years 1992-2022, containing about 64.400 entries,

as a CSV file, along with a statement on his motivations for "liberating" this data (Melançon, 2023).

Transformation to BiBTeX for Zotero

The tabular format provided by Melançon was first transformed into BibTeX using a custom Python script. This BibTeX file was imported into Zotero, where the bibliography can now be consulted. Challenges in the transformation notably include the correct splitting of largely unstructured lists of author and editor names. As a consequence, manual improvement of the data is ongoing, but now considerably facilitated by Zotero's interface.

Analysis of the Data

The bibliographic data in BiBTeX format was also exported, from Zotero, to several other formats, among them Zotero RDF. Using this XML-based format, several analyses have already been performed concerning e.g. the authors, publication types, languages, and patterns of collaboration that can be observed in the bibliography. These and more analyses are provided on a dedicated website, and only a summary of results is presented here.

For example, the four scholars most frequently mentioned as authors or editors of publications are Michel Porret, Jacques Berchtold, Michel Delon and Catriona Seth, all with over 300 publications over a period of 31 years. Also, the dataset is clearly dominated by French-language publications, which make up about 74% of the entries (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of languages in the *XVIIIe: Bibliographie* dataset.

With respect to collaboration patterns, it is notable that co-authorship is clearly an exception (only 6% of publications have more than one author), but that co-editorship is very widespread (60% of publications have two or three editors, while 32% have only one editor). Editors frequently publishing together have been identified and co-editing clusters determined using community detection in Gephi (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Co-editing network for the XVIIIe siècle: Bibliographie dataset, with communities shown by color.

Publication of the data and results

All data analyses have been performed using Python in Jupyter Notebooks. The scripts, results and explanatory prose have been published directly from the notebook files as a website using Quarto for rendering and Github pages as the publication platform.

The following tools were used in this project: Zotero 6.3, <https://www.zotero.org/>, Python 3.10, <https://www.python.org/>, Gephi 0.10.1, <https://gephi.org/>, Quarto 1.3, <https://quarto.org/> and Github pages, <https://pages.github.com/>.

Future Work

Further corrections and refinements will be applied to the dataset on Zotero. When preparing data for analysis, the missing possibility to systematically and explicitly model part-whole relationships between contributions to edited volumes and the edited volumes themselves in Zotero requires attention, as it is a potential source of inflated numbers for editorship in the data. As for analyses, one area of future work concerns thematic trends and patterns, something that requires using external resources such as catalogs to scrape abstracts and/or keywords in order to enable analyses based on more than just the titles. Also, it would be of interest to identify potential biases in the dataset, for example with respect to author gender. Based on author gender identification (which, however, has its own problems; see e.g. Karimi et al. 2016), the distribution of author genders found in the Bibliographie could be compared to that in larger resources like the *Bibliography of the Modern Lan-*

guage Association, when filtering the latter for research on the Eighteenth Century.

Note on language

Because of the international audience of the *Bibliographie*, the website and this abstract have been written in English. The poster would, however, be produced in German for DHd2024.

Bibliographie

Luhmann, Jan, and Manuel Burghardt. 2021. “Digital Humanities—A Discipline in Its Own Right? An Analysis of the Role and Position of Digital Humanities in the Academic Landscape.” *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 73 (2): 148–71. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24533>.

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Schöch, Christof, Julia Dudar, and Evgeniia Fileva, eds. 2023. *Survey of Methods in Computational Literary Studies*. CLS INFRA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892112>.